

A TWO PHASES COUPLING FREE AND POROUS FLOW METHOD AT MULTI-SCALES OF LCM PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

A coupling CHNSD (Cahn-Hilliard-Navier-Stokes-Darcy) two-phase flow model is developed to simulate the Liquid composite molding (LCM) processes at multiple scales. A fiber reinforcement can be considered as a multi-scale porous media with large inter-tow pores and fine intra-tow pores. The Navier-Stokes equation is applied in the large inter-tow pores region, while two phase Darcy's law governs flow in the intra-tow pores considered as a porous medium. The refined "BJS" (Beavers-Joseph-Saffman) condition is included at the coupling interface condition to solve the two phase and two medium coupling problems. Flow flux, normal stress and velocity continuity are also taken into consideration at the interface conditions. Transient resin flow front tracking is carried out by adopting the Cahn-Hilliard equation. First results and validation are presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

LCM (Liquid Composite Molding) processes have various advantages such as low-cost production, and clean and high-efficiency composites manufacturing. In the typical LCM process, resin flows in dry fibrous reinforcement before curing. The filling of reinforcement is a key step which will have a significant and direct influence on the quality and mechanical properties of the final composite part. At the meso-scale, due to the intricate structure of the reinforcement, the resin flow during the impregnation can be considered as free surface flow between tows and porous flow inside tows. At the macro-scale, the flow inside the whole reinforcement can be regarded as a porous flow, while the flow between the wall of the mold and the reinforcement, or inside the flow-net, can be regarded as free surface flow.

Nowadays, the numerical simulation research on the LCM process mostly focus on the porous medium flow. There are few studies for the coupling free flow and porous flow especially in a two phase situation. However, in the actual process of LCM, both types of flows are included.

Hwang and Advani [1] developed a new method to solve the Stokes-Brinkman equation to figure out effective permeability of dual scale fibrous porous media based on this method. Blais et al. [2] proposed a Stokes-Darcy coupled flow model with low permeability of the porous media to simulate the infusion process at macro-scale. However, the Brinkman equation has so far only been applied to solve single-phase coupling problems. It is known that this equation will cause numerous problems in two-phase porous flow [3].

At the micro scale, Stokes equation can be used in the whole flow domain. When the scale is upgraded to meso or macro scales, Darcy's law is suitable to describe the porous flow. For the domain of free flow, Navier-Stokes equation remains available. Nevertheless, the order of these two equations are different, and appropriate conditions should be developed on the interface. The purpose of this study is to setting up a model using numerical methods to solve this coupling two-phase free flow and porous flow problem.

Based on literature studies [3, 4], the goal is to develop a coupling CHNSD (Cahn-Hilliard-Navier-Stokes-Darcy) two-phase flow model in numerical simulation of LCM processes. In this model, the Navier-Stokes equation, which could be simplified by Stokes equation in most classical cases, is applied in the free flow region, while two phase Darcy's law works in the porous medium. The Cahn-Hilliard equation is adopted as the approach to track the transient resin flow front. The refined "BJS" (Beavers-Joseph-Saffman) condition is included at the coupling interface condition to solve the two phase and two medium problems. Flow flux, pressure and velocity continuity are also taken into consideration at the interface conditions to keep the conversation of mass.

2 CONSTRUCTION OF MATHEMATICAL MODEL

2.1 Governing equations in porous flow region

In the porous flow region, there is the continuity equation (1), Darcy's equation (2) and auxiliary equations (3) to determine saturation and pressure at the interphases.

$$\varepsilon \frac{\partial(\rho_f S_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_f \mathbf{u}_{pf}) = \rho_f q_f, \quad f = r \text{ for resin, } a \text{ for air} \quad (1)$$

Where ε is the dimensionless porosity of the porous preform, ρ_f [kg/m³] is the density of the p -phase fluid, S_f is the saturation of f -phase fluid. q_f [1/s] is the source/sink term of p -phase fluid. \mathbf{u}_{pf} is the Darcy's velocity which can be achieved by solving the Darcy's law:

$$\mathbf{u}_{pf} = -\frac{\mathbf{K}_p k_r}{\mu_p} (\nabla p_{pf} - \rho_f \mathbf{g}), \quad f = r, a \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{K}_p is the permeability tensor. For a 2D structure, \mathbf{K}_p can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{xx} & K_{xy} \\ K_{yx} & K_{yy} \end{bmatrix}$$

The principal permeabilities can be defined as K_x and K_y , in this case $K_{xx} = K_x$, $K_{yy} = K_y$, and $K_{xy} = K_{yx} = 0$.

In a first approach, we can consider that the intra tow domain, the two principal transverse permeabilities are the same and equal to k_r , where k_r is the relative permeability determined with the saturation function S_r . $0 \leq S_r \leq 1$, p_{pf} is the pressure of p -phase fluid in porous medium. μ_p is the viscosity of p -phase, \mathbf{g} is the gravity constant. Other auxiliary equations include relationship of saturation and capillary pressure, and are presented below in equation 3.

$$S_r + S_a = 1, \quad P_{pc}(S_r) = P_{pa} - P_{pr} \quad (3)$$

Where P_{pc} is the capillary pressure, P_{pa} and P_{pr} are the pressure of air and resin respectively.

2.2 Governing equations in free flow region

In the spaces between the tows, the flow is governed by the Navier-stokes equation (4) and continuity equation (5):

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_F}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u}_F \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u}_F \right) = \nabla \cdot [-p_F \mathbf{I} + \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u}_F + (\nabla \mathbf{u}_F)^T)] + \rho \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{F} \quad (4)$$

$$\rho \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}_F) = 0 \quad (5)$$

Where ρ [kg/m³] is density, \mathbf{u}_F [m/s] is velocity in free flow region, p_F [Pa] is pressure, \mathbf{F} [N] represents actions of external forces and \mathbf{I} is unit matrix.

For this first approach, the fluid is considered as Newtonian fluid and the Reynolds number is particularly low. Hence, inertial force can be ignored compared with the dominating viscous force, and the Navier-Stokes equation is replaced by Stokes equation.

2.3 Front tracking

To track the flow front, the phase field method with Cahn-Hilliard equation (6) is applied.

$$\begin{cases} \Psi = -\nabla \cdot (e^2 \nabla \phi) + \phi(\phi^2 - 1) \\ \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_F \cdot \nabla \phi = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\gamma \beta}{e^2} \nabla \Psi \right) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Where Ψ is an auxiliary phase field variable, e [m] is the thickness parameter of the interface, ϕ is the phase field variable and it is a dimensionless parameter, the value of ϕ is -1 in the air field while is 1 in the resin field. \mathbf{u}_F [m/s] is the velocity of the fluid. γ is the mobility, and β [N] is the magnitude of the mixing energy.

2.4 Coupling condition on the interface of porous region and free flow region

Since the governing equations are different on the porous region and the free flow region, it is crucial to set suitable coupling interface conditions to combine these two domains to ensure continuity. The continuity of normal flux is governed by the equation 7:

$$\mathbf{u}_F \cdot \mathbf{n}_{pf} = \mathbf{u}_{pf} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{pf} \quad (7)$$

Where \mathbf{n}_{pf} is the normal vector.

The continuity of the normal stress is given by the equation 8:

$$\mathbf{n}_{pf} \cdot [(-p_F \mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\tau}) \mathbf{n}_{pf}] = - \left(\frac{1+\phi}{2} P_{pr} + \frac{1-\phi}{2} P_{pa} \right) = - \left(P_{pr} + \frac{1+\phi}{2} P_{pc} \right) \quad (8)$$

The tangential stress jump condition is applied by refined BJS boundary condition for two-phase flow. The classical BJS condition is only valid for single-phase flow system in principle [5]. When effective permeability and relative permeability are introduced, the BJS condition can be extended to two phase cases as illustrated in eq. 9.

$$\mathbf{t}_{pFi} \cdot [(-P_F \mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\tau}) \mathbf{n}_{pFi}] = -\mathbf{t}_{pFi} \cdot \frac{\mu \eta(S_r)}{\sqrt{K_p k_r(S_r)}} \mathbf{u}_F, \quad i=\{1, 2, \dots, d-1\} \quad (9)$$

\mathbf{t}_{pFi} is the tangent vector, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the viscous stress tensor, $\eta(S_r)$ is the slip factor as a function of S_r and d describes the dimension of RVE (Representative Elementary Volume). Relative permeability $k_r(S_r)$ is a function of saturation S_r .

3 COMPARISON WITH CLASSICAL NAVIER-STOKES METHOD

In a real fiber tow, there are thousands of fibers inside, as shown in figure 1(a) with only about 250 fibers, a 2D section of tows model is set up as presented in figure 1(b). However, if the entire section is taken into consideration as the geometrical model for numerical simulation, the calculation cost is too high. Therefore the study domain is limited to the representative section in the transverse direction presented in figure 1(c). To set up the geometrical model as shown in figure 1(c) applying Navier-Stokes equation, a random fiber configuration code is developed [6, 7] to produce a realistic geometrical fiber tow model.

3.1 Boundary conditions and initial values

Inlet and outlet conditions are set on the left and right boundaries respectively. Symmetry conditions are set on the upper and lower boundaries as illustrated in figure 1(c). Initial values and physical parameters to input into the models for comparison are listed in the table 1.

Figure 1. Research region and geometrical model definition

Parameters	Values
Porosity ε	0.5
Absolute permeability K_p	$1 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$
Density of resin ρ_r	1000 kg/m^3
Density of air ρ_a	10 kg/m^3
Viscosity of resin μ_r	$0.1 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$
Viscosity of air μ_a	$0.01 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$
Inlet pressure	$1.001 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$
Outlet pressure	10^5 Pa
Geometrical model height	0.4 mm
Geometrical model width	1 mm

Table 1. Input parameters of the porous fibrous medium and fluids

3.2 Model applying CHNSD method

To calculate the equivalent permeability in transverse direction of the porous tow, the approach developed in reference [6, 7] is adopted since transverse flow model is only considered in this study. The porosity ε can be calculated by using the equation 10.

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \frac{A_{fiber}}{A_{intra-tow}} \quad (10)$$

Where A_{fiber} is the area of fibers inside the tow region and $A_{intra-tow}$ is the area of entire tow.

For example, when the radius of a single fiber filament is defined as $r_f = 7.8 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, the transverse permeability estimated by eq. 10 is about $1 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$. In this paper, to set up the realistic geometric model in the transverse direction (figure 1(c)), $r_f = 7.8 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ is implemented to obtain the same permeability as the input permeability value in the coupling CHNSD model.

FEM (Finite Element Method) is carried out by applying CFD software COMSOL Multiphysics to discretize the governing equations with free triangular mesh elements. For CHNSD coupling model, classical IMPlicite Pressure Explicite Saturation (IMPES) approach [8] is applied to figure out the solution of pressure and saturation written in PDE (Partial Differential Equation) module in porous medium, coupling interface condition is realized by coding weak form.

3.4 Comparison and verification of flow front at different times

Flow front tracking by numerical methods are listed in figure 2. In figure 2(a), (c), (e) and (g), Navier-Stokes equation is applied while CHNSD coupling method governs the flow in figure 2(b), (d), (f) and (h). Resin appears in blue ($\phi = 1$) and air is in red ($\phi = -1$).

t = 0.001s

t = 0.01s

t = 0.4s

t = 1s

Figure 2. Comparison of flow front tracking process in two methods at different times

Preferable agreement of transient saturation has been achieved at different time steps as illustrated in figure 2. Resin flows much fast in the inter-tow domain, then infuses into the tow step by step. Meanwhile, pressure continuity between free flow domain and porous medium is presented in figure 3. Even though the pressure continuity maintains well at the interface of two different flow domains, the pressure distribution seems to be almost the same value since the initial boundary condition of the pressure difference is only 100 Pa.

Figure 3. Pressure field at time: 0.2s

To obtain an obvious difference of the pressure and velocity distribution at the model domain, pressure difference between inlet and outlet is set as 1000 Pa.

Figure 4. Pressure field at time: 0.002s

In figure 4, pressure distributions of both realistic model and CHNSD coupling method are compared. The result of coupling model meets with the realistic model very well. From the results, we can clearly see the phenomenon that pressure diffuses faster along the interface direction intra tow than inter tow. This can be explained by the porous structure cause the generation of capillary force in the tow domain which has been depicted in equation 8. In the CHNSD coupling method this effect is clearly visible at the interface and disappears when we look away from the interface.

Velocity fields are also studied and illustrated in figure 5.

Figure 5. Velocity field distribution at time: 0.5s

Resin flows faster in the inter-tow domain than in the intra-tow one as shown in figure 5. In fact, the calculated velocity in the intra-tow domain is close to 0 m/s. A detailed plot is presented in figure 6 to describe the velocity distribution on a cut line of the model at the position $x = 0.5$ mm and at the time 0.5s.

(a) Cut line location $x = 0.5 \text{ mm}$

(b) Velocity distribution along the cut line at $x = 0.5 \text{ mm}$, time: 0.5 s

Figure 6. Comparison of the velocity distribution calculated with the two methods

As presented in figure 6(b), curves of velocity distribution achieved by two methods meet each other quite well. For N-S realistic method line, there are several breaking points in the line intra-tow domain since in the realistic model there are fibers at the breaking points. For both curves' intra-tow domains, the velocity all along the cut line stays the same at quite low values, while for inter-tow, the further the position away from the tow, the higher value of the velocity is. This appearance reveals that even in the transient flow, the velocity and pressure distribution will reach and stay in a steady state after a while, and inter-tow resin flow is the dominating velocity contributor in the whole infusion process.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

This work presents a model set up based on CHNSD theory to simulate the LCM processes at meso-scale and to track the flow front of the resin. Results of pressure, velocity and transient saturation are compared and verified with model using the Navier-Stokes equations based on a quasi-realistic geometrical model. We can conclude that with the pressure difference condition set on inlet and outlet, in intra-tow domain, the pressure diffuses in advance than that in inter tow region. In addition, the intra-tow velocity remains the same, while inter-tow velocity increases with the distance from the tow.

Influences of variant parameters as boundary conditions and resin or fiber reinforcement properties can be discussed with this model. Numerical simulation by applying this method can be extended to macro-scale or reinforcement with anisotropic permeabilities and 3D complex geometrical models in future work.

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